

Study on Above and Belowground Biomass and Carbon Stocks of Compartment No.80, 81 and 82 in Kha Paung Reserved Forest, Oaktwin Township, Bago Region

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Abstract

The present study was conducted during July and September in 2017 by laying 4 quadrates (100m × 100m) following random plot sampling method. The total biomass of tree species was 361.485 ton/ha in compartment no.80, 389.969 ton/ha in compartment no.82, 415.951 ton/ha in compartment no.81 (plot-1), and 566.725 ton/ha in compartment no.81 (plot-2). The total carbon stock of tree species was 180.742 ton/ha, in compartment no.80, 194.984 ton/ha in compartment no.82, 207.976 ton/ha in compartment no.81 (plot-1) and 283.362 ton/ha in compartment no.81 (plot-2). The largest biomass as well as carbon content species were *Tectona grandis* L. f. (Kyun) followed by *Gmelina arborea* Roxb., (Yemane), *Terminalia alata* (Heyne) Roth (Htaukkyunt), *Xylocarpus* (Roxb.) Taub (Pyinkado).

Introduction

The global carbon cycle is composed of four major reservoirs: atmosphere, oceans, reserves of fossil fuels and terrestrial ecosystems, including vegetation and soils. Measurements show that the atmospheric carbon concentration has been increased year by year since the beginning of the industrialization (Houghton, 2003). Nature has provided us with natural carbon “sinks” or “sponges” like the terrestrial ecosystem and the oceans. Forest’s ecosystem is one of the most important carbon sinks of the terrestrial ecosystem. Forest’s vegetation takes up the carbon dioxide in the process of photosynthesis (Woodwell *et al.*, 1978). The tropical forests are said to play a major role in the global carbon cycle, storing up to about 46% of the world’s terrestrial carbon pool and about 11.55% of the world’s soil carbon pool, acting as a carbon reservoir and functioning as a constant sink of atmospheric carbon. Trees and woody biomass play important role in the global carbon cycle. Forest biomass account for over 50% of terrestrial carbon stocks. (Cairns *et al.*, 1997, Mokany *et al.*, 2006).

Carbon stock in trees generally accumulate slowly over time. Assessment of the amount of carbon sequestered by a forest will give us an estimate of the amount of carbon emitted into the atmosphere when this particular forest area is deforested or degraded. Furthermore, it will help us to quantify the carbon stocks which in turn will enable us to understand the current status of carbon stocks and also derive the near-future changes in the carbon stocks. The estimation and monitoring of tropical forests carbon is of great relevance for understanding the global cycle and the effects of climate change on forest resources, as well as to fulfill the reporting requirement of international programs, such as the United Nations Reducing Emission from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) (Gibson *et al.*, 2007)

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METHODOLOGY

Study area

The Study Area is situated in West Bago Yoma of Oaktwin district in Bago region. It covers an area of 7762.57 ha (19182 Acres). The present study was conducted in the Kha Paung Reserved Forest, Oaktwin District, Bago region and this area encompasses hills, plains, slopes, valleys, cascades and creeks. The compartment no.80 is possessed 410.93 ha (1015 Acres) altitude between N 18°51'48.1" to N 18° 51'49.6" &E 095°59' 14.4" to E 95° 59'10.7",elevation ranges between 218m to 272m.The compartment no.81 is possessed 387.85 ha (985 Acres) altitude between N 18°51'17.4" to N 18° 51' 19.4" &E 095°59' 23.9" to E 95° 59' 28.1",elevation ranges between 219m to 254m.The compartment no.82 is occupied 224.19 ha (554 Acres) altitude between N 18° 52' 08.6" to N N 18° 52" 11.0' &E 96° 00'28.3" to E 96° 00'26.0", elevation ranges between 253m to 290m.

Climate

The climate of Kha Paung Reserved Forest has three main seasons; extremely hot summer, moist monsoon and cool winter. The monthly rainfall ranges from 0 mm in February and December while 470.40 mm in July in 2017.Moreover, the minimum and maximum temperature range varies from 14.7 °C in December to 38.6 °C in March. The monthly relative humidity ranges from 64% in March to 94% in September.

Fig.2. Histogram showing Monthly rainfall, temperature and relative humidity of 2017

Data collection and species identification

Field investigation was performed in July and September 2017. Four different study sites and vegetation were collected for each site: altitude, aspect, slope, and plant composition at Kha Paung Reserved Forest ecosystem for the present study. Each sample plot (permanent quadrat) 100m × 100m was divided into three areas of 10m × 10m for trees. The information that was recorded from each sample plot includes: height, girth at breast height (GBH) and species names of trees. Height and girth at breast height (GBH) were measured for any woody plant species with height ≥2m and GBH ≥10cm thick, 1.3m from ground level, by using measuring tape. Plant specimens were collected, pressed, dried and matched by checking “A Checklist of Trees, Shrubs, Herbs and Climber of Myanmar” (Kress et al., 2003) and Hundley, H.G. and Chit Ko Ko (1961) and “Flora of Ceylon” (Vol. I-XIV).

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed for species composition, Biomass and Carbon stock. Tree Biomass of study area was used by indirect (non destructive) method. (Pearson *et al.*, 2005). Above ground biomass of the four study sites was estimated using the biomass regression equation developed by Brown *et al.*, (1989). The biomass regression equation developed by Brown et al., (1989) is $Y = 42.69 - 12.800 (D) + 1.242 (D^2)$. The ratio of below ground biomass was estimated as 0.28% of above ground biomass (Mokany et al., 2006). From the computed above ground biomass and then above ground carbon stock was calculated by multiplying each AGB values by 0.5. Carbon is 50% of the dried biomass (Petrokofsky et al., 2012; West, 2009). Above ground biomass and above ground carbon stock (ton/ha) that has been held by the natural forest was quantified from the two methods.

Results

Table 1. Above ground biomass and carbon distribution over GBH class of compartment no.80 and 82

GBH Classes (cm)	compartment no.80			compartment no.82		
	TD	AGB	AG carbon	TD	AGB	AG carbon
	(n ha)	(ton ha)	(ton ha)	(n ha)	(ton ha)	(ton ha)
10 ≤ 50	210	13.671	6.836	190	11.211	5.606
51 ≤ 100	112	51.074	25.537	133	60.277	30.138
101 ≤ 150	42	81.255	40.628	85	130.400	65.200
151 ≤ 200	19	68.989	34.494	37	109.581	54.791
201 ≤ 250	3	15.866	7.933	12	62.552	31.276
251 ≤ 300	1	8.750	4.375	1	6.993	3.496
≥300	2	42.806	21.403	2	28.277	14.138
Total	389	282.410	141.205	460	409.291	204.646

Table 2. Above ground biomass and carbon distribution over GBH class of compartment no.81 (plot-1) and (plot-2)

GBH Classes (cm)	compartment no.81 (plot-1)			compartment no.81 (plot-2)		
	TD	AGB	AG carbon	TD	AGB	AG carbon
	(n ha)	(ton ha)	(ton ha)	(n ha)	(ton ha)	(ton ha)
10 ≤ 50	136	8.787	4.393	358	10.743	5.371
51 ≤ 100	148	75.848	37.924	96	39.523	19.762
101 ≤ 150	67	103.788	51.894	60	89.518	44.759
151 ≤ 200	10	28.611	14.305	40	128.013	64.006
201 ≤ 250	9	50.870	25.435	23	124.899	62.449
251 ≤ 300	5	40.243	20.122	3	24.510	12.255
≥300	1	16.815	8.408	2	25.549	12.775
Total	376	324.962	162.481	582	442.754	221.377

Table 3. Above and below ground biomass (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.80

Study stands	compartment no.80		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Biomass
<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb.	95.100	26.628	121.727
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	59.949	16.786	76.735
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	22.892	6.410	29.301
<i>Mitragyna rotundifolia</i> (Roxb.) Kuntze	17.638	4.939	22.577
<i>Millettia pendula</i> Benth.	10.367	2.903	13.270
	205.945	57.665	263.609
Others	76.465	21.410	97.875
Total	282.410	79.075	361.485

Table 4. Above and below ground biomass (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.82

Study stands	compartment no.82		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Biomass
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	175.117	49.033	224.150
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	46.485	13.016	59.501
<i>Millettia pendula</i> Benth.	23.208	6.498	29.706
<i>Mitragyna rotundifolia</i> (Roxb.) Kuntze	11.838	3.315	15.153
<i>Homalium tomentosum</i> Benth.	7.569	2.119	9.688
	264.217	73.981	338.198
Others	40.446	11.325	51.770
Total	304.663	85.306	389.969

Table 5. Above and below ground biomass (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.81 (plot-1)

Study stands	compartment no.81 (plot-1)		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Biomass
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	94.947	26.585	121.532
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	57.970	16.232	74.201
<i>Terminalia alata</i> (Heyne) Roth	49.087	13.744	62.831
<i>Millettia pendula</i> Benth.	23.165	6.486	29.652
<i>Neonauclea excelsa</i> Blume	12.072	3.380	15.452
	237.240	66.427	303.668
Others	87.721	24.562	112.283
Total	324.962	90.989	415.951

Table 6. Above and below ground biomass (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.81 (plot-2)

Study stands	compartment no.81 (plot-2)		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Biomass
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	176.344	49.376	225.720
<i>Terminalia alata</i> (Heyne) Roth	72.061	20.177	92.239
<i>Xylocarpus xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	36.754	10.291	47.045
<i>Millettia brandisiana</i> Kurz.	22.773	6.377	29.150
<i>Stereospermum personatum</i> (Hassk.) Chatterjee	14.646	4.101	18.747
	322.578	90.322	412.900
Others	120.176	33.649	153.825
Total	442.754	123.971	566.725

Estimating of above ground and below ground biomass

The minimum above ground biomass was 282.410 ton/ha in compartment no.80 while the maximum AGB was 442.754 ton/ha in compartment no.81 (plot-2) and that is by summing up the AGB of each in the sample plot. Below ground biomass followed the same trend as the above ground biomass. The minimum and maximum BGB were 79.075 ton/ha in compartment no.80 and 123.971 ton/ha in compartment no. 81(plot-2).From each tree biomass, the largest AGB of *Tectona grandis* L. f., 176.344 ton/ha in compartment no.81 (plot-2), 175.117 ton/ha in compartment no.82, 94.947 ton/ha in compartment no.81(plot-1) while *Gmelina arborea* Roxb., 95.100 ton/ha in compartment no.80 were observed.

Table 7. Above and below ground carbon (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.80

Study stands	compartment no.80		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Carbon Stock
<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb.	47.550	13.314	60.864
<i>Xylocarpus xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	29.974	8.393	38.367
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	11.446	3.205	14.651
<i>Mitragyna rotundifolia</i> (Roxb.) Kuntze	8.819	2.469	11.288
<i>Millettia pendula</i> Benth.	5.183	1.451	6.635
	102.972	28.832	131.805
Others	38.233	10.705	48.938
Total	141.205	39.537	180.742

Table 8. Above and below ground carbon (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.82

Study stands	compartment no.82		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Carbon Stock
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	87.559	24.516	112.075
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	23.243	6.508	29.751
<i>Millettia pendula</i> Benth.	11.604	3.249	14.853
<i>Mitragyna rotundifolia</i> (Roxb.) Kuntze	5.919	1.657	7.576
<i>Homalium tomentosum</i> Benth.	3.784	1.060	4.844
	132.109	36.990	169.099
Others	20.223	5.662	25.885
Total	152.331	42.653	194.984

Table 9. Above and below ground carbon (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.81 (plot-1)

Study stands	compartment no.81 (plot-1)		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Carbon Stock
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	47.473	13.293	60.766
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	28.985	8.116	37.101
<i>Terminalia alata</i> (Heyne) Roth	24.543	6.872	31.415
<i>Millettia pendula</i> Benth.	11.583	3.243	14.826
<i>Neonauclea excelsa</i> Blume	6.036	1.690	7.726
	118.620	33.214	151.834
Others	43.861	12.281	56.142
Total	162.481	45.495	207.976

Table 10. Above and below ground carbon (ton ha⁻¹) of compartment no.81 (plot-2)

Study stands	compartment no.81 (plot-2)		
	AG Biomass	BG Biomass	Total Carbon Stock
<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.	88.172	24.688	112.860
<i>Terminalia alata</i> (Heyne) Roth	36.031	10.089	46.119
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	18.377	5.146	23.523
<i>Millettia brandisiana</i> Kurz.	11.387	3.188	14.575
<i>Stereospermum personatum</i> (Hassk.) Chatterjee	7.323	2.050	9.373
	161.289	45.161	206.450
Others	60.088	16.825	76.912
Total	221.377	61.986	283.363

Above ground and below ground carbon stock

The maximum and minimum above ground carbon content were 582 individual trees of 221.377 t/ha in compartment no.81(plot-2) and 389 individual trees 141.205 t/ha in compartment no.80. Maximum and minimum below ground carbon stock were 61.986 ton/ha in compartment no. 81(plot-2) and 141.205 ton/ha in compartment no.80. From each tree carbon stock, the largest above ground carbon stock of *Tectona grandis* L. f., 88.172 ton/ha in compartment no.81(plot-2), 87.559 ton/ha in 82, 47.473 ton/ha in 81(plot-1) while *Gmelina arborea* Roxb., 47.550 ton/ha in compartment no.80 were occurred.

Discussion and Conclusion

Based on the result of the four study sites, a total number of 389 individuals, belonging to 46 species, 40 genera, and 22 families were sampled in compartment no.80, 460 individuals, belonging to 35 species, 34 genera, and 22 families in compartment no.82, 376 individuals, belonging to 40 species, 33 genera, and 20 families in compartment no.81 (plot-1), 582 individuals, belonging to 48 species, 43 genera, and 19 families in compartment no.81 (plot-2). Alternation of species composition affects the future ecosystem integrity and sustainability. (Swamy *et al.* 2010).

Regional terrestrial carbon accounting is very important to global climate change particularly in tropical areas. In the current study attempted an estimation of biomass and carbon stock with emphasis on above ground standing biomass. Biomass and Carbon sequestration varies from forest type and age of forest and carbon sequestration potential is rely on tree size class. Tropical rain forest has the highest potential of carbon sequestration and followed by the dry evergreen forest and the mixed deciduous forest respectively. (Terakunpisut *et al.*, 2007). Of the global scale secondary forest are important carbon sink, that partially compensates for carbon emission form tropical deforestation. (Houghton *et al.*, 2000, Pan *et al.*, 2001). The above ground biomass differs with sites, successional stages of the forest, disturbance levels species composition etc. (Whitmore, 1984; Brunig, 1983).

In the present study sites, the largest biomass as well as carbon content species may be concluded that *Tectona grandis* L. f. (Kyun) followed by *Gmelina arborea* Roxb. (Yemanae), *Terminalia alata* (Heyne) Roth, *Xylia xylocarpa* (Roxb.) Taub (Pyinkado), respectively (Table 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10). The study result in the different compartment and different tree species of study area show that as the tree increases basal area and biomass also increase. According to biological statistics, based on species composition, basal area, estimated biomass and carbon stocks values in the present study sites among them compartment no.81 (plot-1) may be significant than other compartments, although compartment no.80 further improved by applying protected and sustainable forest management (Table 1 and 2).

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